

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

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EFFICACY OF INSULIN PUMP IN GLYCEMIC CONTROL AMONG PATIENTS
WITH TYPE 1 DIABETES

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this study was to evaluate the efficacy of insulin pump administration in improving glycemic control in patients with Type 1 diabetes compared to management via multiple daily insulin injections (MDI). HgbA1c level was identified as the outcome measure of glycemic control.

Patients were identified by the researcher via an electronic database of patients on insulin pump and MDI therapy who met the inclusion criteria. All patients with odd numbers assigned to them were selected for inclusion in this study. Thirty subjects on insulin pumps and 30 on MDI were selected for participation. Data were collected via chart review using a data collection tool developed by the researcher to collect information on the subjects' age, gender, ethnicity, and age of onset of diabetes. HgbA1c level, body mass index (BMI) and total daily dose of insulin were also collected at baseline, as well as 3, 6, 12, and 24 months post insulin therapy. The baseline and post insulin therapy at 3, 6, 12, and 24 months allowed the researcher to evaluate the efficacy of insulin pump in improving glycemic control as compared to MDI.

There was no statistically significantly difference between the two groups for age, gender, ethnicity, BMI, HgbA1c and total daily insulin doses. Several conclusions were reached. It was found that insulin pump and MDI have similar effects on glycemic control over a 24-month period of time. Further research of larger and more heterogeneous samples would be likely provide a better assessment of the efficacy of insulin pump therapy in comparison to MDI therapy.

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INTRODUCTION

The number of people with diabetes in the United States has increased rapidly in the past few years due to population growth, aging, urbanization, increased prevalence of obesity, and physical inactivity (Wild, Roglic, Green, Sicree, & King, 2004). According to the American Diabetes Association (as cited in the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC], 2011), approximately 18.8 million Americans are diagnosed with diabetes in 2010, approximately 3 million with Type 1, about 7 million are undiagnosed, and about 79 million people are pre-diabetic. The increasing prevalence of diabetes and the multiple complications associated with poor control of the disease cost billions of dollars in treatment and prevention programs (CDC, 2011). However, in spite of strategies and efforts made by prevention and treatment campaigns, the number of deaths associated with diabetes and its complications is still rapidly increasing (Wild et al., 2004). Consequently, diabetes management needs to be optimized to prevent complications and mortality associated with this disease. In patients with diabetes, despite high doses of insulin, glycemic control is often a challenge. It is therefore crucial to improve glycemic control among patients with diabetes by optimizing insulin therapy to prevent complications and mortality associated with this disease. The use of an insulin pump is associated with improved glycemic control (Leinung, Thompson, Luo, Leykina, & Nardacci, 2012). Unfortunately, insulin pumps add on another cost factor in the management of diabetes. Nonetheless, it is cost effective to keep patients out of the hospital due to Diabetic Acidosis (DKA) and hypoglycemic episodes. In addition, the long-term complications associated with the disease such as renal failure, which leads to hemodialysis, are more costly than an insulin pump and its related equipment and

supplies. Research has demonstrated that the insulin pump is effective in reducing hemoglobin A1C (HgbA1c), therefore minimizing the progression of complications of diabetes. Because of the paucity of research and conflicting findings about this topic, future research on the efficacy of the insulin pump in improving glycemic control is needed. There is also a need to determine whether confounding variables impact glycemic control depending on the method of insulin administration.

Background of the Study

Despite the fact that there is no cure for diabetes, the associated medical regimen has come a long way to help patients stabilize their blood glucose levels within more acceptable ranges to reduce their risk of long-term complications. Today, many new devices such as insulin pumps can help patients improve glucose control and avoid rigid rules and loss of freedom typically associated with the management of this disease. An insulin pump is a small external device approximately the size of a standard pager that ensures continuous low dose delivery of rapid or short acting insulin in the subcutaneous tissue. It is attached to a thin plastic tube with soft cannula that is inserted under the skin, usually on the abdomen (Skyler, Ponder, & Kruger, 2007). However, some patients use their thighs, lower back, or arms as alternative infusion site.

Intensive insulin therapy via an insulin pump significantly reduces the risk of complications in patients with diabetes (Thabit, 2012). It is becoming endocrinologists' preferred treatment modality to achieve glycemic control among patients with Type 1 diabetes. Large randomized trials have found that use of insulin pumps yielded significant reduction in the development and progression of complications associated with diabetes (Skyler et al., 2007). Nevertheless, improvement with glycemic control as

measured by HgbA1c is often associated with increased frequency of severe hypoglycemia (Nielsen et al., 2005). As a result, patients and clinicians' fear of hypoglycemia has become a significant barrier to optimizing diabetes management via this method of insulin administration. Recent studies demonstrate that insulin pump therapy with rapid acting insulin analogs not only improves glucose control but also decreases rates of severe hypoglycemia compared with multiple daily injections (Skyler et al., 2007). In addition, many patients with poor diabetes control are at high risk for macrovascular and microvascular complications such as renal failure, heart disease, blindness, and amputation. Because of the significant number and severity of complications associated with diabetes, the benefit of glucose control has motivated many clinicians to use insulin pumps for diabetes management. The Diabetes Control and Complications Trial (DCCT) demonstrated that better glycemetic control with fewer hypoglycemia events is achievable with insulin pump therapy (The Diabetes Control and Complications Trial Research Group [DCCT], 1993). As discussed by Thabit (2012), the DCCT data clearly demonstrate that insulin pump use has many potential benefits for diabetes patients. Pump therapy offers a physiological mode of insulin administration that results in fewer hypoglycemia episodes and decreases blood sugar variability (Grzanka et al., 2012). As a result, patients on insulin pumps have improved HgbA1c levels and good diabetes control. Consequently, clinicians who choose to incorporate insulin pumps in their optimal diabetes management strategies have the opportunity to reduce significant hypoglycemia events and blood glucose variability in their diabetes patients.

Statement of the Problem

Diabetes is associated with multiple complications and increased mortality. However, improved glycemic control can decrease the microvascular and macrovascular complications associated with Type 1 diabetes mellitus. It is a constant challenge for providers to optimize glycemic control while minimizing severe hypoglycemia episodes and weight gain. Intensive therapy with an insulin pump can improve glycemic control among patients with Type 1 diabetes by lowering HgbA1c levels and decreasing recurrent hypoglycemia events and high blood glucose variability.

According to Yeh et al. (2012), only been a few studies have demonstrated consistent findings related to the efficacy of insulin pump use versus multiple daily insulin dosage among patients with Type 1 diabetes. Insulin pump therapy results in a high degree of patient satisfaction with decrease risk of severe hypoglycemia (Barnard et al., 2007). Furthermore, some studies have yielded mixed results regarding the safety and effectiveness of insulin pump therapy. One study found decreased HgbA1c levels in the first few months of insulin pump therapy but noted a return to pre-pump status after a year of using the insulin pump (Plotnick, Clark, Brancati, & Erlinger, 2003). Several conflicting findings in the literature about the efficacy of pump therapy could likely be attributed to small sample size, short follow up duration, limited ethnic diversity, and failure to account for confounding variables (Yeh et al., 2012). Therefore, with these factors in mind, the current study was thought to be useful as it was designed to look at a more diverse group of patients with Type 1 diabetes, including a longer treatment follow up period of time for up to 2 years post pump therapy, and attempting to account for as many confounding variables as possible.

Lowering HgbA1c is often a challenge for clinicians due to non-compliance with medical regimen among patients with diabetes. It also poses more risks of hypoglycemia with rebound hyperglycemia. In addition, improvement in diabetes control cannot be measured just by lowered HgbA1c alone. Severe or recurrent hypoglycemia with rebound hyperglycemia and high blood glucose variability can potentially affect the true value of HgbA1c, often rendering it an unreliable tool or measure of diabetes control. Therefore, it is crucial for clinicians to assess for recurrent hypoglycemia that can potentiate rebound hyperglycemia rather than looking at HgbA1c alone. Insulin pump use can lower HgbA1c and reduce recurrent hypoglycemia while generating a wide variability of blood glucose results. Insulin pumps are not utilized widely in clinical practice, likely due to inconsistent findings about their efficacy and safety in diabetes control among patients. Many patients are reluctant to wear a device that can be cumbersome, less cost-effective, and insufficiently efficacious. In addition, most insurance policies do not cover the insulin pump and supplies at 100% cost. Thus, insulin pump usage can be costly to many patients who have to pay out of pocket.

Despite the fact that insulin pump therapy plays an important role in managing Type 1 diabetes, further research needs to identify the cost effectiveness and clinical outcome of insulin pump management in patients with Type 1 diabetes. This research study assessed the efficacy of insulin pump therapy in improving glycemic control among patients with Type 1 diabetes. Consequently, the results of this study will indicate whether the use of insulin pumps can optimize diabetes management among patients with Type 1 diabetes while also reducing hypoglycemia events.

Purpose of the Study

The aim of this study was to evaluate the efficacy of insulin pumps in improving glycemic control in patients with Type 1 diabetes compared to management via multiple daily insulin injections. Glycemic control in this study was defined as HgbA1c less than seven percent with fewer than five episodes of hypoglycemia in a week. Patients with Type 1 diabetes using both insulin pumps and multiple insulin injections were evaluated by measuring their HgbA1c levels, total daily insulin dose, and weight at baseline and at 3, 6, 12, and 24 months post insulin pump therapy. Data on other potential confounding variables (i.e., age, ethnicity, comorbidity, body mass index [BMI], weight, age of onset of diabetes) were collected to investigate whether these variables had an impact on glycemic control. The efficacy of insulin pumps in maintaining glycemic control was assessed by comparing HgbA1c level with other key variables at baseline and after several months of treatment.

Research Questions

This study attempted to answer the following three research questions:

1. How effective is insulin pump therapy in improving glycemic control among patients with Type 1 diabetes in comparison to multiple daily insulin injections?
2. What effects do other patient characteristics (e.g., age, BMI, gender and ethnicity) have on glycemic control based on the method of insulin administration?

3. What effects do insulin therapy have on HgbA1c levels, BMI and total daily dose insulin at 3, 6, 12 and 24 months post initiation of insulin pump therapy compared to multiple daily dose injections?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Electronic databases including Cinahl, PubMed, Cochrane Library, and Google scholar were searched from 2000-2013 to identify relevant studies that addressed whether insulin pump therapy is effective in achieving glycemic control among Type 1 diabetes patients. According to several published research studies, there are numerous benefits of using insulin pump therapy for diabetes management, including improved glycemic control, reduced rates of blood glucose variability, decrease in insulin dose needed, and reduction in hypoglycemia episodes (Barnard et al., 2007). Improved glycemic control can reduce microvascular and macrovascular complications associated with Type 1 diabetes (Bergenstal et al., 2010). Providers are often challenged to optimize glucose control while minimizing severe hypoglycemia, glucose variability, and weight gain (Thabit, 2012). Moreover, clinicians tend to be reluctant to start patients on insulin pumps due to fear of hypoglycemia, DKA, non-adherence, and high cost associated with the pumps, which might inhibit widespread adoption of insulin pumps among patients with diabetes (Barnard et al., 2007).

Adherence to a diabetes regimen is the key to optimizing diabetes control. However, non-adherence is a major challenge among clinicians taking care of patients with diabetes. The medical and psychological literature suggests that regimen complexity is one of the primary factors associated with low adherence rates (Ary, Toobert, Wilson, & Russell, 1986). Ary et al. (1986) reported that there is greater adherence to dietary and physical activity components of the diabetes regimen in comparison to medication and glucose monitoring. In addition, a review of literature identified some of the barriers of insulin pump usage. Ary and colleagues concluded that

these barriers could be overcome if studies can demonstrate that continuous insulin infusion or insulin pump use is beneficial and cost effective in managing Type 1 diabetes, as well as pointing to improvements in health outcomes that outweigh the increased cost of insulin pumps.

Continuous insulin infusion via an insulin pump is a promising therapy; however, the clinical evidence supporting its use has been inconsistent (Bergental et al., 2010). Plotnick et al. (2003) noted in their review of the literature that most of the studies on this topic had small samples, limited ethnic diversity, and inconsistent findings, which could be attributed to confounding variables such as age, duration of diabetes, and social and environmental factors.

A parallel group 24-week randomized study by Raskin et al. (2003) compared the efficacy, safety, and patient satisfaction of continuous insulin infusion versus multiple daily injections. The findings of this study demonstrate that the insulin pump is an excellent alternative to multiple dose insulin therapy for diabetes patients who are capable, motivated, and trained to use the device. However, the HgbA1c results were similar for both groups from baseline to the end of the study. Therefore, there was no statistically significant difference between the two groups. Although there was no difference in reduction of HgbA1c among insulin pump users, participants still preferred using the insulin pump over multiple injections due to convenience, flexibility, and ease of use. As a result, overall treatment satisfaction was statistically significant among insulin pump users.

Another random control trial among older adults with Type 2 diabetes was conducted by Herman et al. (2005). This study included 107 participants who were

randomly assigned to continuous insulin infusion or multiple daily injections for a year. Subjects were over 60 years of age, used insulin one or more times per day at baseline, and had mean baseline mean of HgbA1c of 8.4 for continuous insulin infusion and 8.1 for multiple daily insulin injections. After 1 year, HgbA1c was significantly reduced compared to baseline for both groups. However, there was no statistically significant difference between groups. These two large trials demonstrated that continuous insulin infusion reduces HgbA1c and is preferred by users; however, clinical superiority to multiple daily insulin injections was not demonstrated.

Other smaller randomized trials have found mean HgbA1c reduction in favor of continuous insulin infusion; however, these findings were not statistically significant. A cross over design study by Wainstein et al. (2005) found reduction of mean HgbA1c favoring continuous insulin infusion over multiple daily insulin injections among Type 2 diabetes patients. The subjects were randomized to continuous insulin infusion with insulin lispro and multiple daily injections with regular insulin doses and NPH for 18 weeks. The mean HgbA1c end of treatment effect among subjects who completed the study was -.08% reduction for continuous subcutaneous insulin infusion while multiple daily insulin doses had .4% reduction (Wainstein et al. 2005). This finding demonstrated a statistically significant difference between the two groups.

The first longitudinal long term study of continuous subcutaneous insulin infusion (CSII) among individuals with Type 2 diabetes was conducted with 59 subjects randomized to two simple dosing regimens. Group A had a fixed basal rate; pre-prandial boluses were adjusted to achieve postprandial levels of less than 180. In contrast, Group B subjects had no boluses and a fixed daytime basal rate, and their nighttime basal rate

was adjusted in order to attain fasting blood glucose of less than 120mg/dl. HgbA1c levels decreased similarly for both groups for years 1, 2, and 3. In addition, the reduction in HgbA1c was significant from baseline to years 1, 2, and 3. Secondary measures such as hypoglycemia, weight gain, and quality of life were similar among the groups (Labrose-Lhermine, Cazals, Ruidavets, & Hanaiare, 2007).

Studies by Edelman et al. (2010) and Parker et al. (2008) provided evidence for a simple dosing regimen in a short-term 4-month study. Parker et al.'s study had 21 subjects randomized to receive equal doses of insulin via continuous subcutaneous insulin infusion (CSII) or once daily injection of insulin glargine followed by a crossover to another therapy. Although no dosage adjustments for glycemic variability were made and doses were equivalent, CSII use was associated with lower variability in exogenous fasting insulin levels. In contrast, Edelman et al. conducted a 4-month longitudinal pilot study of 60 subjects divided into three equal cohorts who were switched from their baseline treatment to CSII. Initial recommended starting dose on the pump was 0.5 times the patient weight, with half being given as a single basal rate and the remainder divided into three meal boluses. Mean HgbA1c levels were reduced significantly in all three cohorts after 4 months of therapy.

Another randomized study by Doyle et al. (2004) compared the efficacy of insulin pump with multiple injections using insulin glargine. Thirty-two Type 1 diabetes mellitus patients were randomly assigned to receive either multiple daily dose or continuous insulin infusion. Dose titration in both groups was based on home self-monitored blood glucose measurement. Monthly HgbA1c levels, total daily dose, blood glucose readings, and adverse events were compared after 16 weeks of therapy. No

significant change was found in HgbA1c. Baseline HgbA1c level was 8.2 versus 8.1 for the multiple daily dose group over 16 weeks of therapy. In contrast, patients on insulin pumps had a sharp reduction in HgbA1c from 8.1 to 7.2 after 16 weeks of therapy. Total daily insulin dose was unchanged in the multiple daily dose group, but significantly dropped with the pump group. Fasting self-monitored blood glucose was similar in both groups. However, lunch, dinner, and bedtime readings were significantly lower in the pump group.

A study by Hanaire-Broutin, Melki, Bessieres-Lacombe, and Taubert (2000) compared the efficacy of two intensified insulin regimens: continuous insulin infusion and multiple daily injections by using short acting insulin analog lispro in Type 1 DM patients. A total of 41 patients age 43.5 +/-10.3 years, 21 men and 20 women, were included in an open label randomized crossover study. The researchers found that HgbA1c, blood glucose levels, and insulin doses were significantly lower with continuous insulin infusion. In addition, the frequency of hypoglycemia episodes did not differ significantly between the two treatment modalities.

Grzanka et al. (2012) divided a sample of 140 Type 1 diabetes mellitus patients into two subgroups according based on age to estimate treatment outcomes in young adult patients in comparison with older adults. The study found that younger individuals had significantly worse treatment outcomes compared to older adults. However, the findings remained unclear. Grzanka et al. posited that this difference could be attributed to less adherence in checking blood glucose and less frequent use of advanced pump features, which may be due to age-dependent behaviors, social environment, or both.

Nielsen et al. (2005) conducted a study to investigate whether the insulin given as a subcutaneous continuous infusion would result in an improvement in glucose homeostasis. Four patients with uncontrolled Type 2 diabetes on high doses of insulin and oral hypoglycemic agents were started on insulin pump therapy. Findings of this study showed a significant improvement in plasma glucose concentrations with a reduced HgbA1c level and marked decrease in insulin dosages as daily requirement.

A meta-analysis and systematic review study by Yeh et al. (2012) via MEDLINE, EMBASE, and the Cochrane Central Register of Controlled trials through February 2012 yielded many studies with inconsistent findings. In randomized and controlled studies, multiple daily dose and CSII showed similar effects on HgbA1c levels and the incidence of severe hypoglycemia in children and adults with Type 1 diabetes and adults with Type 2 diabetes. In addition, for adults with Type 1 diabetes, HgbA1c level decreased more with CSII than with multiple daily dose insulin, but one study heavily influenced these results. Nevertheless, many of these studies had a variety of limitations, such as small sample size, short duration, and samples of mainly Caucasians.

METHODS

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework guiding this study was Donabedian's (1985) Theory of Quality Health Care. Donabedian defined quality health care based on a triad of elements: structures of care, processes of care, and outcomes of care. Structure refers to equipment and facilities as well as human resources, which includes the services available to patients and clinicians' expertise (Mitchell, Ferketich, & Jennings, 1988). Processes refers to how care is provided, relying on the structures to provide resources and mechanisms for participants to carry out patient care activities (Donabedian, 1985). In addition, processes are performed in order to improve patient health in terms of promoting recovery, functional restoration, survival, patient satisfaction, and quality of life. Outcomes refer to results from medical care that was provided to the patient (Mitchell et al., 1988).

In this study, the insulin pump was referred to as the structure based on Donabedian's (1985) conceptual framework. Processes in this study referred to how patients' insulin pump settings, including blood glucose and total daily insulin dose, would be reviewed by clinicians to ensure the accuracy of the insulin pump setting. Furthermore, reviewing blood tests such as HgbA1c, pump data, and blood glucose levels will enable clinicians to assess the efficacy of insulin pumps in improving glycemic control among patients with diabetes. Blood glucose and HgbA1c levels are the results of care or outcomes in this study, based on Donabedian's conceptual framework.

To illustrate how the Donabedian (1985) framework guides practice, the following example is given. In Kaiser Permanente South Bay's Endocrinology

department where patients with diabetes are being managed, a physician may consider utilizing a structure change. Physicians may order insulin pumps for all Type 1 diabetic patient to coordinate better care. The insulin pump is the new structure being utilized as information technology that provides patients' downloads such as glucose readings and amount of insulin and carbohydrates taken, and identifies results that need actions or interventions. Patients' glucose results, frequency of blood sugar measurements, amount of insulin administered, carbohydrate intake, and adherence information can be downloaded from the insulin pump. The downloaded information from the insulin pump allows the clinician to assess and evaluate diabetes control and not have to rely on HgbA1c, which is often not reliable for determining glucose control among patients with high glucose variability. This process of downloading information from the insulin pump could also be modified through a standard protocol to guide clinicians on how to collect and interpret the information. Outcomes from using an insulin pump include improved patient satisfaction, lower blood glucose levels, and decreased insulin use and carbohydrate intake.

Research Design

The design of this research was a retrospective cross sectional study via chart review. A total of 60 patients being seen in the Endocrinology Department at Kaiser Permanente South Bay at the time of the data collection (January 2014) were selected as subjects for this study. Sixty subjects were selected as the sample in this study. They were divided into two groups: 30 subjects with Type 1 diabetes (DM) on insulin pumps and 30 on multiple daily insulin dose injections. Patient data such as HgbA1c levels, weight, and total daily insulin dose were assessed at baseline and after 3, 6, 12, and 24

months of therapy. The independent variable in this study was the method of insulin administration: either pump therapy or multiple insulin dose injections. The dependent variables were weight, total daily insulin dose, and HgbA1c.

Protection of Human Rights

The proposal was sent to both Kaiser Permanente South Bay and CSULB Institutional Review Boards for a review to assure that patient confidentiality and human rights were protected. Patient identification number and the assigned study participant number were entered into a log book that was kept in a locked drawer at the agency agreeing to this study. The hospital identification number was not entered into the study computer database. Instead, a study identification number, rather than health care agency patient medical record number, was entered into the computer program used for data collection. Only data required for the study, as identified in the data collection tool, were collected from patients' charts or electronic medical records and analyzed. The researcher was the only individual gathering information from the patients' electronic medical records.

Setting

The study was conducted in the Endocrinology Department in one of a number of facilities that are part of a large health maintenance organization. The department cares for approximately 300 adult patients with Type1 DM from the ages of 18-88 years old. Three board certified endocrinologists and the researcher are the providers of specialized health care services for patients in this setting.

Sample Selection

Sixty patients with Type 1 diabetes either on insulin pump therapy or multiple daily dose insulin injections were selected as subjects for this study. Because the study was a retrospective chart review of demographic and physiologic data related to care of patients with Type 1 DM, all patients from 18-88 years of age who were currently receiving services for their Type I DM patients in the endocrine practice in January 2014 were eligible for participation in this study. However, exclusion criteria were put in place to control for certain confounding variables. Thus, the researcher excluded patients who had any of the following: less than 2 years of insulin pump use, Type 2 DM, a history of ischemic heart disease or stroke within the last 12 months, advanced nephropathy as evidenced by proteinuria or serum creatinine greater than 2, liver enzymes twice above the upper limits of the normal range, frequent recurrence of hypoglycemia, multiple hospitalizations for DKA, and HgbA1c above 15 at baseline. Frequent hypoglycemia was defined in this study as five or more hypoglycemia episodes per week. Multiple hospitalizations was defined as three or more hospitalizations in a month. Patients with a history of hemolytic anemia or hemoglobinopathy such as sickle cell, G6PD, and vitamin B12 and folate deficiency were also excluded because HgbA1c is not considered a suitable test to determine glucose control in these patients (Koenig et al., 1976). Furthermore, patients who were noncompliant with the insulin pump regimen were excluded. For this study, noncompliance was defined as suspending or temporarily discontinuing use of the pump for over an hour daily.

Methodology

Data were collected via chart review of 60 patients with Type 1 DM who were on either insulin pump administration or multiple daily insulin injections. Thirty patients on insulin pumps and 30 patients on multiple daily insulin dose injections were selected via convenience sampling. The following strategy was put in place for sample selection. Patients with Type 1 DM were identified by the researcher via an electronic database of patients on insulin pumps and multiple daily dose insulin who met the inclusion criteria. Patient whose course of Type 1 diabetes was further complicated by exclusion criteria were eliminated as subjects. The total population who met all criteria for multiple daily injection (MDI) administration and the total number of pump users composed the population of interest. The population of interest numbered 168. Subjects were then divided into two groups based on the type of insulin administration. Sequential numbers were assigned to all eligible patients in each of the two groups to identify them. All patients with odd number assigned to them were selected for inclusion in this study.

Because the researcher was interested in key Type 1 diabetes physiologic changes over a 2-year period from when a subject was first switched to pump administration of insulin, the researcher first reviewed the chart of each pump subject to determine the date of insulin pump initiation. That determined eligibility for inclusion in the insulin pump group. Through careful chart review, the researcher then collected data at time of pump initiation (pre) and time series data over the 2-years (post) related to the variables relevant to this study.

Demographic data such as age, gender, ethnicity, weight, BMI, duration of diabetes, and pre and post data including HgbA1c level, total daily insulin doses, and

weight were collected by the researcher via chart review on the subjects selected as insulin pump users. The subjects' HgbA1c levels both pre and post insulin pump therapy were determined as well as any episodes of hypoglycemia and DKA requiring hospitalization via chart review. Information noted in patients' charts as to HgbA1c levels, total daily insulin use, and body weight both pre and post insulin pump therapy were recorded at baseline and at 3, 6, 12 and 24 months post insulin pump usage. Insulin doses were recorded with weight to allow reliable comparison and to capture the relationship between weight and insulin needs of individual patients. Of note, the timeframe relative to the data recorded for each subject in the insulin pump group varied as individual patients began pump therapy at different points in time.

For the multiple daily insulin injection group, the researcher collected the first recorded HgbA1c result along with the patient's corresponding weight and total daily insulin dose found in the patient's chart and identified these values as the patient's baseline data. The researcher then recorded subsequent data such as HgbA1c, total daily insulin use and weight at 3, 6, 12 and 24 months. Therefore, the data were collected for a period of 2 years in patients assigned to the MDI group. The researcher reviewed patients' charts and collected the same study variable information for the MDI users as was collected for insulin pump users. At the end of data collection, 2 years of data were obtained, and the researcher was then able to compare data from both groups.

A data collection tool was developed by the researcher to collect information on the subjects' age, gender, ethnicity, BMI, weight, duration of diabetes, HgbA1c, body weight, total daily insulin doses, DKA, and hypoglycemic events. The baseline and post pump therapy data at 3, 6, 12, and 24 months allowed the researcher to evaluate the

efficacy of the insulin pump in improving glycemic control as compared to administering MDI of insulin.

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using SPSS statistical analysis software. For continuous variables such as age, weight, BMI, duration of diabetes and HgbA1c, descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation were calculated. The researcher conducted Chi-Square and t-tests analysis as appropriate to the type of data; a repeated measure ANOVA was used to compare each row of data set such as HgbA1c, weight, and total daily insulin dose of the same subject at same points in time.

RESULTS

A total of 128 patients were screened for the study and 60 were divided into two groups based on the method of insulin administration. The mean age of the sample was 52 (minimum age 19, maximum age 81). Almost half (45%) of the sample was primarily Caucasian; Hispanics represented 22% of the sample, followed by 18% Asians, eight percent African Americans, and seven percent indicating other. Over half of the subjects in both groups were male, with a mean age of 24 at initiation of the insulin pump. In contrast the MDI group at baseline of data collection had a mean age of 31. There was no statistically significant difference between the two groups in terms of age, gender, BMI, and ethnicity (see Tables 1-6).

Table 1

*Demographic Characteristics of Study Participants: Ethnicity * Pump Crosstab*

Ethnicity	Method of Insulin Administration		Total
	Multiple Daily Injections	Pump	
White	11	14	25
African American	4	2	6
Asian	4	6	10
Hispanic	7	6	13
Other	4	2	6
Total	30	30	60

Table 2

*Demographic Characteristics of Study Participants: Ethnicity * Pump Chi-Square Tests*

Statistic	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	2.180 ^a	4	.704
Likelihood Ratio	2.200	4	.699
Linear-by-Linear Association	.627	1	.428
N of Valid Cases	60		

^a = Four cells (40.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 3.00.

Table 3

*Demographic Characteristics of Study Participants: Gender * Pump Crosstab*

Gender	Method of Insulin Administration		Total
	Multiple Daily Injections	Pump	
Male	18	20	38
Female	12	10	
Total	30	30	60

Table 4

*Demographic Characteristics of Study Participants: Gender * Pump Chi-Square Tests*

Statistic	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	.287 ^a	1	.592		
Continuity Correction ^b	.072	1	.789		
Likelihood Ratio	.287	1	.592		
Fisher's Exact Test				.789	.395
Linear-by-Linear Association	.282	1	.592		
N of Valid Cases	60				

^a = 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 11.00.

^b = Computed only for a 2x2 table.

Table 5

Group Statistics: Age and Baseline Body Mass Index (BMI)

Variable	Pump	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Age	Multiple Daily Injections	52.83	14.244	2.601
	Pump	51.83	13.217	2.413
BMI Baseline	Multiple Daily Injections	25.23	3.794	.693
	Pump	25.80	3.418	.624

Note. $N = 30$.

Table 6

Independent Samples Test of Age and Body Mass Index (BMI)

Variable	Condition	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Age	Equal variances assumed	.702	.406	.085	58	.933	.300	3.548	-6.801	7.401
	Equal variances not assumed			.085	57.679	.933	.300	3.548	-6.802	7.402
BMI Baseline	Equal variances assumed	.317	.576	-.608	58	.546	-.567	.932	-2.433	1.300
	Equal variances not assumed			-.608	57.381	.546	-.567	.932	-2.433	1.300

Effect of Method of Insulin Delivery on HgbA1c Levels

In order to determine the impact of insulin pump administration on HgbA1c levels compared to multiple daily injection delivery in a sample of 60 subjects, a series of repeated-measures ANOVAs were conducted. This type of statistical analysis was

required in order to compare the two study groups on numeric outcomes at five time points. Because the dataset provided information on the same person for five points in time, a repeated measure design was used. A Mauchly's test was performed; the results indicated that the assumption of sphericity had been violated ($\chi^2(9) = 34.22, p < 0.001$); therefore, degrees of freedom were corrected using a Greenhouse-Geisser estimate of sphericity ($\epsilon = 0.70$).

The resulting repeated measures ANOVA revealed a statistically significant effect for time ($F(2.8, 128.80) = 2.82, p = .04$), with overall HgBA1c scores of patients at baseline ($M = 8.56, SD = 1.80$) decreasing by 24-month follow-up ($M = 8.07, SD = 1.71$). In addition, a statistically significant main effect was observed for protocol (method of insulin administration; $F(1, 46) = 6.42, p = .02$), with pump users having statistically significantly lower HgBA1c scores ($M = 7.74, SE = 0.29$) than those receiving multiple daily injections ($M = 8.88, SE = 0.34$). However, examination of the interaction between time and protocol revealed no significant difference in the trajectory of HgBA1c scores between those using an insulin pump compared to those receiving multiple daily injections ($F(2.80, 128.80) = 2.50, p = .07$). The ever so slightly downward sloping lines representing the HgBA1 levels for each group is demonstrated in Figure 1. There is a fairly consistent gap between the two lines, with MDI subjects having consistently higher scores over time.

Figure 1. Trend of HgbA1c levels in samples using insulin pump and MDI over 2 years.

Analysis revealed a significant difference between the groups at the start of data collection as to their baseline HgbA1C levels; with the insulin pump users having statistically significant lower HgbA1c levels at baseline. Although after 24 months there was no statistically significant difference in the degree of lowering HgBA1c between the two methods of insulin administration, data revealed a trend in insulin pump users toward lowering their HgBA1C levels to a point close to statistical significance as compared to MDI ($p = .07$). Figure 1 presents a graph of mean HgBA1c in a 2-year period for both groups.

Insulin Dose and Method of Administration

Because the dataset provided information on the same person for five points in time, a repeated measure design was used to determine the effect of method of administration and the dose of insulin prescribed to manage the subjects. Mauchly's test

was conducted and indicated that the assumption of sphericity had been violated ($\chi^2(9) = 69.13, p < 0.001$, therefore degrees of freedom were corrected using a Greenhouse-Geisser estimate of sphericity ($\epsilon = 0.60$).

The resulting repeated measures ANOVA revealed no statistically significant main effect for time ($F(2.41, 89.06) = 1.82, p = .16$). Similarly, the absence of a statistically significant main effect for protocol suggested no statistically meaningful differences in total insulin dose between insulin pump users and those receiving multiple daily injections ($F(1, 37) = 2.34, p = .13$).

Examination of the interaction between time and protocol (method of insulin administration) revealed no significant difference in the trajectory of insulin dose recorded between those using an insulin pump compared to those receiving multiple daily injections ($F(2.41, 89.06, p = .33)$). Figure 2 presents a graph of mean insulin doses over a 2-year period in both groups.

Body Weight and Method of Insulin Administration

Body weight is watched carefully in the administration of insulin, as insulin administration is associated with weight gain and higher doses typically result in additional weight gain. Again, body weight (measured in kilograms) was collected at five points in time. Mauchly's test was performed and indicated that the assumption of sphericity had been violated ($\chi^2(9) = 148.27, p < 0.001$; therefore, degrees of freedom were corrected using a Greenhouse-Geisser estimate of sphericity ($\epsilon = 0.48$).

Figure 2. Trend of mean insulin doses in samples using insulin pump and MDI over 2 years.

The resulting repeated measures ANOVA revealed no statistically significant main effect for time ($F(1.93, 88.83) = 0.87, p = .42$). Similarly, the absence of a statistically significant main effect for protocol suggested no statistically meaningful difference in the body weights of insulin pump users and those receiving multiple daily injections ($F(1, 46) = 0.38, p = .54$). An examination of the interaction between time and protocol revealed no significant difference in the trajectory of body weights recorded between those using an insulin pump compared to those receiving multiple daily injections ($F(1.93, 88.83) = 0.63, p = .53$). Figure 3 presents a graph to compare mean body weight in both groups over a 2-year period.

Figure 3. Trend of mean body weight in insulin pump users and MDI over 2 years.

DISCUSSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This retrospective study was conducted in a large diabetes clinic that is part of a large health maintenance organization. The study compared HgbA1c levels in a relatively small sample of patients managed on insulin pumps ($N = 30$) and multiple daily dose insulin injections ($N = 30$). This researcher's findings revealed data similar to those demonstrated in previous research investigations reported in the literature over the past 14 years (Herman et al., 2005; Raskin et al., 2003, Wainstain et al., 2005; Yeh et al., 2012). The study results indicated that the use of insulin pump when compared to MDI administration did not demonstrate a statistically significant difference in terms of glycemic control measured by HgbA1c. This study examined the relationship of HgbA1c, total daily insulin doses, and weight over a 2-year period of time between two groups: first time insulin pump users versus those who continued with their management plan of MDI injections. However, as noted previously, a trend in the direction of statistical significance was noted. Thus the possibility of a type II error should be considered given the fairly small sample size and the fact that only subjects with data from all five time-points were kept in the analysis.

At the conclusion of the formal statistical analysis, the researcher decided to revisit the data, observing some interesting trends in the data worthy of discussion and potential analysis in a future study. Specifically, as the amount of insulin increased over time, the HgbA1c value decreased. Nevertheless, there were three instances when the insulin dose was decreased in a patient in the MDI group despite the fact that the HgbA1c had gone up. This observation has clinical implications in terms of trying to understand what prompted the healthcare provider to lower the insulin dose when intuitively it

should have been raised to achieve better glycemic control. One likely explanation reflects practice patterns; namely, clinicians frequently make changes with insulin doses based on recent glucose readings for 2-4 weeks rather than just looking at the HgbA1c alone. This may not be the best management practice and deserves further investigation.

The analysis demonstrated that in the study sample, weight did not change despite increased daily insulin dose: an atypical finding given that increased insulin dose is associated with weight gain. However, it could be that the subjects in this sample may have been more active or exercised regularly; therefore, their weight may have generally stayed the same. The researcher did not collect data on subjects' exercise regimens; therefore the issue of whether exercise was a confounding factor could not be addressed in this study. Hence, insulin dosage in relationship to HgbA1c levels physical activity and weight needs further investigation. In addition, this study noted that the patient with poor glycemic control HgbA1c, greater than 9, obtained the greatest benefit: lower HgbA1c compared to baseline with either method. For example, in the MDI group one subject had a baseline HgbA1c of 16 and two subjects had levels of 14; subsequently, their levels were lowered to 10 following 2 years of MDI therapy. In contrast, the insulin pump users' baseline HgbA1c of 10 or more dropped by 2-3 points over 2 years of insulin pump therapy.

It is noteworthy that those who adopted pump administration and stayed on it for at least 2 years had significantly lower HgbA1c levels at baseline than their counterparts. This lasting effect could likely be attributed to the fact that the insulin pump has more physiological insulin delivery than MDI administration. In addition, the degree of flexibility and convenience that insulin pumps offer to their users (e.g., users may modify

their infusion rate by the hour to tailor to their activity such as exercise, delayed meals, or sleeping in) will lead to greater adherence in managing their chronic condition. One could also speculate that patients who pay directly for insulin pump supplies are more determined and motivated to optimize their diabetes control.

Because there was a trend noted in the data toward a significant difference in lowering in HgbA1c in insulin pump usage versus MDI administration, this would support continuing this study using a larger sample size and further data collection. It is possible that a small effect was not detected because of the small sample size in this study. Therefore, it would be worthwhile to continue the study and add more subjects to see whether the results would reach statistical significance between the two groups. The observation of a modest, although nonsignificant, trend toward improved glycemic control with insulin pump use as noted in this analysis is consistent with findings from previous studies noted in the review of literature conducted prior to the launch of this project (Herman et al., 2005; Wainstain et al., 2005).

The researcher recognizes three important limitations in this study: incomplete data such as missing HgbA1c, weight, and total daily dose via data collection tool; a small sample size, therefore small effect was not detected; and the omission of data on whether the patient wore a continuous glucose monitor (CGM). Using a CGM is helpful to some degree as it can decrease variations in blood sugar that could affect HgbA1c values by alerting the patient to high and low glucose levels. Dietary control such as carbohydrate intake was also not assessed. Diet plays an important role in glycemic control; therefore, it is important to incorporate data on diet as well as exercise regimen,

as these are key factors influencing glycemic control. However, self-report of diet and exercise is often a flawed measure.

Hypoglycemic episodes were not assessed due to the retrospective nature of the study and the lack of valid medical record data for hypoglycemia other than self-report. Investigating the incidence and degree of hypoglycemia may confer a greater understanding of the benefit or lack of benefit related to insulin pump use in patients, especially those with baseline HgbA1c close to goal (i.e., if the patient is close to his/her HgbA1c goal, does the use of an insulin pump predispose him/her to more frequent hypoglycemic episodes?). It would also assist the clinician in understanding the finding of decreased insulin dosing associated with higher HgbA1c.

In addition, a secondary analysis of outliers for subjects in both groups whose baseline HgbA1c levels were over 10 and had improvement of more than 2 points in their 2-year post insulin therapy should be conducted to determine whether these outlier subjects had significant impact on the study's research findings.

Further research of larger and more heterogeneous samples would be of benefit and provide a better assessment of the efficacy of insulin pump therapy in comparison to MDI therapy. Additional research is needed to investigate other factors such as fasting blood sugar levels, adherence to therapy, use of continuous glucose monitor, and whether a provider's own practice style impacts glycemic control among patients with Type 1 diabetes either on insulin pump or MDI therapy. It is also important to determine whether insulin pump reduces hypoglycemia and DKA rates among Type 1 diabetics, as these variables could impact glycemic control and reduce complications associated with diabetes.

The researcher plans to disseminate the findings of this study to regional and local nursing research committees meetings and conferences. The initial presentation was conducted by poster and oral presentation at a regional nursing research meeting scheduled for March 26, 2014. The findings of this preliminary study will also be presented during departmental meeting with the endocrinologists and hospital administrators scheduled for May 2014. The researcher plans to continue data collection to increase the sample size to achieve an adequate number of subjects and will continue with data analysis and fine-tuning of this project.

Despite research findings that there are no statistically significant differences between the insulin pump and MDI group in terms of glycemic control, insulin pump data revealed a trend toward lowering HgbA1c levels to a point close to statistical significance. Therefore, incorporating more insulin pump therapy in endocrinology practice would be beneficial, especially to those patients who are failing conventional MDI therapy on large doses of insulin with severe insulin resistance.

Given current research on insulin pump versus multiple daily dose injections on glycemic control, insulin pump use is the becoming preferred treatment modality for Type 1 diabetes. This method of insulin therapy should be considered in patients who are failing conventional multiple daily insulin injections. It may also become the treatment of choice for Type 2 diabetes patients who have severe insulin resistance and have failed multiple daily dose injections. Achieving the lowest possible HgbA1c level without frequent or severe hypoglycemia should be the goal of every clinician in managing patients with diabetes. If this is achievable with insulin pump use, then it should be the

therapy of choice for all diabetes patients, whether Type 1 or Type 2, to prevent or reduce long-term complications associated with poorly controlled diabetes.

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